

The Effect of Digital Literacy and Printed Books on Student Learning Outcomes in Elementary School Gugus 2 Tlanakan Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to (1) analyse the effect of digital literacy and printed books on student learning outcomes in the area of Gugus 2 Tlanakan Sub-district, Pamekasan Regency. (2) To analyse the effect of digital literacy on student learning outcomes in the area of Gugus 2 Tlanakan Sub-district, Pamekasan Regency. (3) To analyse the effect of printed books on student learning outcomes in the area of Gugus 2 Tlanakan sub-district, Pamekasan regency. The research method used is a descriptive method with a quantitative approach. The results of the analysis show that there is (1) an influence of digital literacy and the use of printed books on the learning outcomes of elementary school students in Elementary School Gugus 2 Tlanakan Sub-district, Pamekasan Regency. (2) There is an influence of digital literacy on the learning outcomes of primary school students in Elementary School Gugus 2 Tlanakan Sub-district, Pamekasan Regency. (3) There is an effect of using printed books on the learning outcomes of primary school students in Elementary School Gugus 2 Tlanakan Sub-district, Pamekasan Regency. This study concludes that there is an effect of digital literacy and the use of printed books on the learning outcomes of primary school students in Elementary School Gugus 2 Tlanakan Sub-district, Pamekasan Regency. There is an effect of digital literacy on the learning outcomes of primary school students in Elementary School Gugus 2 Tlanakan Sub-district, Pamekasan Regency. There is an effect of using printed books on the learning outcomes of primary school students at Elementary School Gugus 2, Tlanakan sub-district, Pamekasan Regency.

KEYWORDS: Digital literacy, Learning outcomes, Textbooks

INTRODUCTION

Institutions and education are now influenced by media digitisation. This is characterised by learning activities that already use modern information and communication technology. If effectiveness and efficiency are ignored by users, the results will have a negative impact on anyone who uses it (Balya et al., 2018). Learners are actually used to searching for information on the internet and organising it into a concept or learning material. They also admit that they often look for answers to questions or information about subject matter through digital media rather than reading books. They think that with the search engine on their smartphone, it is easier to get information and more practical. Digital media can cause problems as quoted from Hastjarjo (Rahardjo et. al, 2013), although young people are increasingly accustomed to using new media, as a source and support in their activities to express themselves and establish social relationships, they often have limited ability to examine and criticise the new media itself.

Based on the results of observations and interviews conducted by the author in educational institutions, especially in Gugus 2 Tlanakan District, Pamekasan Regency, which houses 5 elementary schools, namely (Elementary School Gugul 1, Elementary School Gugul 3, Elementary School Larangan Slampar 1, Elementary School Larangan Slampar 2 and Elementary School Taro'an 1), 80% of students admitted that they were not proficient in using the internet as a digital literacy medium, so they mostly used printed books provided by the school in the library. The school has actually scheduled students once a week with a duration of 1 lesson hour to learn to use computers as a digital literacy medium, but due to the limited computer media available, students must take turns when practicing digital literacy, with this incident, of course the results are also not very good and maximum, but at least students have been equipped with theories about the use of digital literacy. Digital literacy is the interest, attitude and ability of individuals who directly use digital technology and communication tools to access, manage, integrate, analyse and evaluate information, build new knowledge, create and communicate with others in order to participate effectively in society (Dea, 2017).

Hague (2015) defines digital literacy as an individual's ability to apply functional skills to digital devices so that one can find and select information, think critically, be creative, collaborate with others, communicate effectively, and remain mindful of electronic security and the evolving socio-cultural context. In the context of education, good digital literacy also plays a role in developing one's knowledge of certain subject matter by encouraging students' curiosity and creativity, (Hagu, 2015). Students are

one of the users of information. The information students need is not only in printed format. The internet began to present information in a different format, namely digital. The information is presented through various facilities provided by the internet such as websites, weblogs, or mailing lists. Assignments are very easy to complete with the development of the internet and digital technology. This phenomenon has led to the emergence of scientific reference sources that are available in digital form and can be accessed to get millions of information that is useful for completing school assignments. To achieve maximum learning outcomes in the learning process, digital literacy not only requires a person to use digital devices well, but also to understand everything related to digital technology.

In addition to discussing the lack of maximum use of digital literacy due to the small number of computers (school computer facilities), another factor in the form of unstable signals, I as a researcher will also discuss the effect of packet book literacy or printed books on student learning outcomes. The definition of package books according to Jamaludin (2015) package books are infrastructure for a number of ready-to-use knowledge to create conditions and an active learning atmosphere. Meanwhile, according to Widodo (2020) a package book is a source of knowledge that is in it that is already tangible or in physical form. Package books or learning resources as educational facilities to support the success of the teaching and learning process. Learning facilities are good learning conditions. Facilities determine the guarantee of the implementation of the teaching and learning process. However, the achievement of educational goals depends a lot on how the teaching and learning process is designed and carried out optimally and for the creation of dynamic and innovative learning. Package books are a means of education to increase success in the teaching and learning process. Tarigan, (2016) says that a package book is a standard book, which contains certain subject matter, and is compiled by experts in certain fields with instructional purposes equipped with educational support tools on certain subject matter and is easily understood by users.

Based on some of the explanations above, it can be concluded that the package book is a means of teaching and learning activities so that students are active in learning and increase student interest, so that the package book is a tool to increase students' learning activities in learning. Devi (2021) in her research stated that the effect of using package books is one way or method to facilitate students in carrying out the learning process. By using package books, students can be encouraged to be more enthusiastic about learning because in the package book there are pictures as explanatory information, not only there is writing in it so that it can attract the attention of students to study it. Package books can not only be used for students but can also be used as a teacher's guide in teaching. Furthermore, in addition to discussing digital literacy and packet book literacy, researchers will also discuss learning outcomes, Nana (2015) argues that learning outcomes are the abilities possessed by students after students receive their learning experience. Meanwhile, Suharsimi Arikunto (2012) defines learning outcomes as the end result after experiencing the learning process, the changes appear in actions that can be observed and can be measured.

According to Dimiyati (2016), learning outcomes are the result of an interaction of learning and teaching actions. From the teacher's side, the teaching action ends with the process of evaluating learning outcomes. From the student's side, learning outcomes are the end of the penggal and the culmination of the learning process. Learning outcomes are partly a result of the teacher's actions, an achievement of teaching objectives, namely maximum learning outcomes. Regarding the learning outcomes of students in Gugus 2 Tlanakan Sub-district, Pamekasan Regency, after making observations in schools under Gugus 2, it shows that the learning outcomes of students' social studies subjects are still less than optimal. In addition to increasing the ability of students to use or access digital literacy, so that they only rely on old-fashioned literacy, namely packaged or printed books / LKS alone, so that students' insights are very limited to existing books.

METHODOLOGY

The research method used is a descriptive method with a quantitative approach. This method is called a quantitative method because the research data is in the form of numbers and analyses using statistics. Quantitative research methods can be interpreted as research methods based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research on certain populations or samples, sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection using research instruments, data analysis is quantitative / statistical with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses (Sugiyono, 2014).

In this study, the population was all grade IV elementary school students in Gugus 2 Tlanakan District, Pamekasan Regency totalling 99 students. The research sample is population because this study will describe all literacy activities in cluster 2. data collection techniques with observation, documents, and questionnaires. Data analysis techniques using inferential statistical analysis

is to determine the effect of independent variables (The effect of proficiency in using digital media and printed books on student learning outcomes at Elementary School Gugus 2 Tlanakan District, Pamekasan Regency) both together and partially. With a significance level of 0.5%.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effect of digital literacy and the use of printed books on learning outcomes of primary school students in cluster 2 of Tlanakan Sub-district, Pamekasan Regency 2023

The simultaneous effect shows the results of the analysis in table 4.7 above, it can be seen that there is a significant influence between digital literacy (X1), and the use of package books (X2) on student learning outcomes (Y). With a value of Fcount = 65.569 with a significant 0.000. When 2 variables are collaborated, students are easier to understand the material delivered by the teacher, so it is natural that the effect is large. The test results can be seen in the following table.

Table 1. Anova^b D Test Results

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	542.490	2	271.245	65.569	.000 ^b
	Residual	4675.833	96	48.707		
	Total	5218.323	98			

a. Dependent Variable: Learning outcomes

b. Predictors: (Constant), digital literacy.

Simultaneously or together, it shows that there is a significant effect of literacy (X1) and the use of printed books (X2), on the learning outcomes of grade V students at Elementary School in cluster 2 Tlanakan District, Pamekasan Regency 2023, which is 65.569% with a significance value of 0.000. Based on the results of the research above and supported by several previous studies such as those conducted by N.K. Widiastini (2021), The Effect of Digital Literacy Through the Use of Melajah.Id on Reading Learning Outcomes. Digital literacy student learning outcomes there is an effect of implementing digital literacy by utilizing melajah.id on reading learning outcomes. Furthermore, research conducted by Zahratun Nisa (2022), The Effect of Digital Literacy and Learning Independence on Economic Learning Outcomes Digital Literacy Learning Independence The results of his research are digital literacy has a significant effect on economic learning outcomes, both discuss digital literacy and learning outcomes old research discusses learning independence.

Dede Salim Nahdi (2020), The Effect of Digital Literacy and Print Books on Student Learning Outcomes Elementary School Taro'an 1 Tlanakan District, Pamekasan Regency Digital literacy, print books Learning outcomes The results showed that most students have basic skills on the internet, they can find and retrieve information from the internet, and use it effectively. Nahriyah (2020), Effect of Digital Literacy Ability of Social Science Education Students on Learning Achievement Digital Literacy, learning achievement Anova analysis results, digital literacy skills have a positive impact on student learning achievement during the online-based learning process. the same discusses digital literacy. With the support of the above empirical studies, researchers have confidence that together digital literacy (X1), the use of package books (X2) on the learning outcomes of fifth grade students at Elementary School in cluster 2 Tlanakan District, Pamekasan Regency 2023. which is 65.57% with a significance value of 0.000. While the remaining 34.43% is determined by other variables/factors not discussed in this study such as parental education, home distance and so on. In the current era of digitalization, digital literacy is very necessary, considering that students prefer to read material via the internet compared to package books, the reason is, digital literacy is more interesting, more colorful, more choices with a variety of school materials.

The influence of Digital Literacy on the learning outcomes of fifth grade students at Elementary School gugus 2 Tlanakan Sub-district, Pamekasan Regency 2023

From the calculation of multiple regression tests, it is found that the effect of digital literacy on learning outcomes has an effect of 60.90%, this can be seen in the following table.

Table 2. Multiple Regression Test Output

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	4,665	4,673		1,640	,000
	Digital Literacy	,335	,065	,283	6,090	,000
	Print book	,318	,053	,305	4,892	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Learning outcomes

Based on the results of data analysis conducted partially, it shows that there is an effect of digital literacy (X1) on the learning outcomes of fifth grade students at Elementary School gugus 2 Tlanakan District, Pamekasan Regency 2023. It can be concluded that digital literacy has a positive effect on the learning outcomes of fifth grade students at Elementary School gugus 2 Tlanakan District, Pamekasan Regency 2023, which is 60.90% or rounded up to 61%. This means that the more often teachers remind students to use digital literacy, the better the learning outcomes of fifth grade students at Elementary School gugus 2 Tlanakan District, Pamekasan Regency 2023. When viewed from the results of the above research, it is clear that digital literacy has a major influence on the learning outcomes of fifth grade students at Elementary School gugus 2 Tlanakan District, Pamekasan Regency. Now the most important thing is that schools need to equip wifi media so that all students can do digital literacy well and how students can make the best use of literacy so that hopefully learning outcomes will improve.

The results of the analysis above are the results of very important information regarding the use of digital literacy, this is one of the electronic media that can be used by students to add interesting reading references and many variants. To get digital literacy is certainly not difficult, simply put, each of the majority of students already has a cellphone, so it can be maximized to improve literacy. In the process of teaching and learning activities at school, literacy is a person's ability to process and understand information in writing or reading. Literacy can be said to be a factor that affects the high and low learning outcomes of students because as students, they should be able to understand information when writing or reading. The main purpose of this understanding is that students are expected to be good at writing and reading, and so that learning objectives can be achieved.

The results of the above research are supported by research conducted by Abdul Latip (2022), The effect of digital literacy on student learning outcomes in chemistry learning. The results show that the level of digital literacy of students has a significant effect on student learning outcomes in distance learning chemistry. Nahriyah (2020), Effect of Digital Literacy Ability of Social Science Education Students on Learning Achievement Digital Literacy, learning achievement Anova analysis results, digital literacy ability has a positive impact on student learning achievement during the online-based learning process. the same discusses digital literacy.

As the concept of literacy developed, the term began to be widely used in various scientific fields integrated with specific fields of study regarding learning outcomes. Literacy is then considered as a means of communication and information retrieval. In accordance with the times and developed according to the scientific field concerned. There are many different fields of study that identify communication as an aspect of literacy. This shows that digital literacy cannot be separated from the needs of students in developing scientific materials and knowledge. The impact of digital literacy will affect the views and thinking patterns of its users. For example, if someone often watches bad news then they will think the world is hopeless. So, sadness and chaos content should not be watched by children. To make matters more complicated, the habit of accessing certain content is captured by digital media service providers so that users will be given similar recommendations continuously. Once trapped, it is difficult for users to change the pattern.

The implementation of the digital literacy program in thematic learning is expected to encourage students and other school residents to support 21st century skills. Critical thinker, namely students are encouraged to think critically and be able to solve problems by being given problems in learning, provoked to ask questions, and try to find solutions to problems by searching for various information via the internet. Students also become more Communicator, where learners are trained to understand and communicate ideas. After understanding what is learned, students are encouraged to share ideas that have become ideas as what they have obtained through the learning process.

The effect of using printed books on the learning outcomes of fifth grade students at Elementary School gugus 2 Tlanakan Sub-district, Pamekasan Regency 2023

From the calculation of multiple regression tests, it is found that the effect of digital literacy on learning outcomes has an effect of 48.92%, this can be seen through the following table.

Table 3. Multiple Regression Test Output

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized		
		Coefficients		Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	4,665	4,673		1,640	,000
	Digital Literacy	,335	,065	,283	6,090	,000
	Print book	,318	,053	,305	4,892	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Learning outcomes

Based on the results of data analysis conducted partially, it shows that there is an effect of using printed books on the learning outcomes of fifth grade students at Elementary School gugus 2 Tlanakan District, Pamekasan Regency 2023. It can be concluded that the effect of using printed books has a positive effect on the learning outcomes of fifth grade students at Elementary School gugus 2 Tlanakan Subdistrict, Pamekasan Regency 2023 by 48.92%. This means that if the teacher encourages students to use printed books in learning, the learning outcomes of fifth grade students at Elementary School gugus 2 Tlanakan District, Pamekasan Regency 2023. Judging from these findings, the effect of using printed books on the learning outcomes of fifth grade students at Elementary School gugus 2 Tlanakan Subdistrict, Pamekasan Regency 2023 is quite large even though it is below 50%. We realize that however, the use of printed books is still irreplaceable, because printed books do not require sophisticated equipment, it is enough to come to the library and borrow from the library staff and we can read them repeatedly without having to refill credit like digital literacy.

Teachers must realize the importance of using printed books, not all students like it but at least still facilitate students who do not have complete facilities regarding reading literacy both at home and at school. There are many types of books that can be studied by students such as (1) Books are written materials in the form of sheets and bound which contain knowledge derived from the basic competencies contained in the applicable curriculum to be used by students, (2) Handouts are everything that is given to students when participating in learning activities. So, handouts are made with the aim of facilitating and making it easier for students to get information or learning materials as a student reference source, (3) Modules are teaching materials written with the aim that students can learn independently without or with teacher guidance, modules contain learning instructions, competencies to be achieved, subject matter content, supporting information, work instructions, practice questions, evaluation, and feedback on evaluation results. The findings above are supported by previous research, namely Aan Anisah (2021), The Influence of the Use of Textbooks and the Internet as a Learning Source on Student Learning Outcomes in Social Studies The use of Internet textbooks Learning outcomes. there is an influence on the use of textbooks and the internet as a learning resource on learning outcomes in social studies subjects at Elementary School 1 Palimanan, Cirebon Regency.

In another study mentioned by Pudji Hariati Ningsih (2021), The effect of using modules and using package books on the learning outcomes of social studies subjects for grade V students of Elementary School Sukabumi The use of modules The use of package books Learning outcomes concluded that social studies teachers have different perceptions of digital literacy skills, and several recommendations were given based on these findings. Latifah Prihandini (2020), The influence of parental attention and the use of printed books on the social studies learning outcomes of grade V elementary school students in the second group of Pengasih sub-district, Kulon Progo district in the 2020/2021 school year Parental attention, printed books learning outcomes The results of hypothesis testing show that there is a positive and significant influence between the use of printed books on the social studies learning outcomes of grade V elementary school students in the second group of Pengasih sub-district, Kulon Progo district. From the explanation above and some support from several, the researchers concluded that students in grade V at Elementary School gugus 2 Tlanakan District, Pamekasan Regency are more interested in using digital literacy than printed book literacy, the reason

they are more interested in using digital literacy is because the variety of material there is more complete, more and more interesting to read.

CONCLUSION

From the above explanation, it can be concluded that (1) there is an influence of digital literacy and the use of printed books on the learning outcomes of primary school students in Elementary School Gugus 2 Tlanakan Subdistrict, Pamekasan Regency, (2) there is an influence of digital literacy on the learning outcomes of primary school students in Elementary School Gugus 2 Tlanakan Subdistrict, Pamekasan Regency and (3) there is an influence of the use of printed books on the learning outcomes of primary school students in Elementary School Gugus 2 Tlanakan Subdistrict, Pamekasan Regency so that it is in accordance with the results of observations made by researchers during pre-research.

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